

A Shallow Water Channel Characterization for Underwater Acoustic Telemetry

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Abstract—We describe a model useful for characterizing shallow water environments for evaluating communications concepts. Some comparisons between experiment and simulation for a variety of conditions are shown.

I. INTRODUCTION

The determination of a "best" signal architecture for a given underwater environment is very difficult, especially for shallow water. We have previously described a model [1] for simulating underwater acoustic telemetry channels in order to test candidate architectures. The model represents the channel as a time varying linear filter which is implemented by a time varying impulse response, coherence time, and Doppler spread strength and bandwidth between source and receiver.

We describe here results from a series of tests that were performed under a variety of shallow water conditions to further test the model and to increase the library of model characterization parameters. Some results from a deep water test are included for comparison.

The tests were also used to explore the importance of coherence time, reverberation time, and Doppler spread on various communication signal architectures and how these parameters vary with direct vs. indirect path, source motion etc.

II. MODEL REVIEW

To model the system we construct the simulated received signal $Z(t)$ from the contributions, $Z_i(t)$, made by each differentiable path,

$$Z(t) = \sum_i Z_i(t). \quad (1)$$

Paths are differentiable, not by rays, but by different Doppler characteristics.

Typically in shallow water, one path is sufficient. For each path,

$$Z_i(t) = \int dt_0 s(t_0 - \tau_i(t_0)) h_i(t - t_0, t_0) \quad (2)$$

where $h_i(t-t_0, t_0)$ is the time varying impulse response and $\tau_i(t)$ is the path delay.

The nonstationary impulse response is implemented by a smooth overlapped superposition of responses to source packets of duration $2\tau_{ci}$ and overlap τ_{ci} where τ_{ci} is the coherence time of the channel. Given the time separation is τ_{ci} , the various impulse responses can be considered as statistically independent. This simulates a nonstationary impulse response with the proper coherence interval.

The time delay is described as

$$\tau_i(t) = \tau_{oi}(t) + \tau_{ir}(t), \quad (3)$$

where $\tau_{oi}(t)$ and $\tau_{ir}(t)$ are the deterministic and random components respectively. We use a first order Gaussian Markov model of $\tau_{ir}(t)$ where $\tau_{ir}(t)$ is generated from statistically independent zero mean unit variance Gaussian samples $x(k)$ and the algorithm

$$\tau_{ir}(t_{k+1}) = \tau_{ir}(t_k)\rho_{12} + \sigma_{\tau_i}\sqrt{1-\rho_{12}^2}x(k) \quad (4)$$

σ_{τ_i} is the standard deviation of τ_{iR} and ρ_{12} is the normalized correlation coefficient

$$\rho_{12} = e^{\mu|t_{k+1}-t_k|} \quad (5)$$

To determine σ_{τ_i} note that the baseband representation of (2) for a cw transmission is

$$cw(t) = \int dt_0 h(t-t_0, t_0) e^{-j\omega_0 \tau(t_0)} \quad (6)$$

For the typical case where $h(t-t_0, t_0)$ is of short duration, τ_r , relative to the inverse bandwidth of $e^{-j\omega_0 \tau(t_0)}$, (6) can be approximated by

$$\begin{aligned} cw(t) &= e^{-j\omega_0 \tau(t)} \int dt_0 h(t-t_0, t_0) \\ &= e^{-j\omega_0 \tau(t)} H(0, t), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $H(0, t)$ is the nonstationary Fourier transform of h at the center frequency.

Thus,

$$\arg(cw) = -\omega_0 \tau(t) + \arg(H) \quad (8)$$

and, for statistical independence,

$$\sigma_{\omega_0 \tau}^2 = \sigma_{\arg(cw)}^2 - \sigma_{\arg(H)}^2 \quad (9)$$

Using the measured cw and simulated impulse responses, $\sigma_{\arg(H)}^2$ and $\sigma_{\arg(cw)}^2$ are determined and $\sigma_{\omega_0 \tau}^2$ computed.

The inverse time constant μ must then be chosen or selected to match experimental observations.

III. DESCRIPTION OF TESTS

Measurements from two different shallow water field experiments are described. Some results from a deep water test are also described.

The location of the first test was in Narragansett Bay, Rhode Island in 67 foot water depth. The experiment was performed on March

20, 1991. The receiver was 10 feet below the surface and located at the end of a pier. The source was deployed 50 feet below the surface off an anchored ship. Omni transducers were used. The range was 530 yards. Wind speed was about 12 knots.

The second shallow water test took place in 200 feet deep water, near Block Island off the coast of Rhode Island at 40 degrees north and 71 degrees west. The tests were performed August 18-19, 1992, with calm, rolling seas and typically a 10 knot wind speed. Two stationary omnidirectional receivers were used, one was suspended 175 feet from the surface and the other on the sea floor. Four test geometries were executed:

1. Stationary omnidirectional source at a range of 258 yards, within the direct path at a depth of 100 feet.

2. Stationary omnidirectional source at a range of 1242 yards, beyond the direct path, at a depth of 100 feet.

3. Omnidirectional source towed under a V-fin at 10 knots at a depth of 100 feet, at a constant radius of 300 yards and within the direct path. Our goal was to test with source motion but with minimal Doppler.

4. Towed source of #3 on a 5000 yard straight traverse at 10 knots at a depth of 100 feet past the fixed receivers with closest point of approach equal to 100 yards. The goal was to test with source motion and Doppler.

The deep water test occurred June 8-18 of 1992 off Eleuthra Island in the Bahamas at a location of about 75 degrees west and 25 degrees north. The depth of the water is about 18,000 feet. The test lasted 10 days with calm, sunny weather, sea state 1 with a 12 knot wind, throughout the test. For most of the test, the source and receiver and were located 3000 feet off the bottom. They both were constant in azimuth with ± 40 degree beam angles in elevation. The horizontal separation between them was 5 nautical miles.

One test was conducted with an omni source located 100 feet from the surface at a range of 5 nautical miles from the receiver.

The following waveforms were used

MFSK: Two frequency banks at 9-10 & 10 -11kHz with 160 lines/bank, sequentially transmitted, for an information rate of 240 bits/sec.

DPSK 10ms: Nineteen bit differential phase shift keyed signal transmitted once per second with bit durations of 0.5 ms.

DPSK 20ms: Nineteen bit differential phase shift keyed signal transmitted once per second with bit durations of 1 ms.

Probe signals for the model were

1. 5 sec 10 kHz cw tones to determine τ_c and Doppler terms.
2. 1ms pulses and 5 second pseudorandom white noise transmissions over the band of 6 to 14 kHz with 100 Hz line spacing to obtain impulse responses.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL AND SIMULATED PARAMETERS

The model constants determined for each simulation are shown in Table 1.

model par location	τ_c ms	τ_r ms	$\sigma_{\omega\Omega\tau}$ rad	μ sec ⁻¹
Narr. Bay	212	7	2.85	.28
BI 258 s	161est	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 258 b	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 1242 s	249	10	1.69	.19
BI 1242 b	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 300 cir s	265est	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI st line s	265est	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI st line b	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
Eleuthra deep-deep	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
Eleuthra surface-deep	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd

BI 258 s = Block Island, 258 yard, suspended receiver

TABLE 1. MODEL CONSTANTS

Table 2 compares experimental and simulated normalized base band envelope magnitude and baseband argument standard deviations.

V. EXPERIMENTAL BIT ERROR RATES

Bit error rates for the different signals and experimental configurations are shown in Table 3 along with their associated signal to noise ratios per bit.

VI. SIMULATED BIT ERROR RATES

Bit error rates for the different signals and simulated configurations are shown in Table 4.

Kundsen noise equivalent to the experimentally determined noise levels was added to the source waveforms for the simulations.

	Experiment	Experiment		Simulation	Simulation
	$\sigma_{ c_w } / \langle c_w \rangle$	$\sigma_{\arg(c_w)}$ Radians		$\sigma_{ c_w } / \langle c_w \rangle$	$\sigma_{\arg(c_w)}$ Radians
Location					
Narr. Bay	.294	2.9		.336	tbd
BI 258 s	.44	8.9		tbd	tbd
BI 258 b	tbd	tbd		tbd	tbd
BI 1242 s	.39	3.1		tbd	tbd
BI 1242 b	tbd	tbd		tbd	tbd
BI 300 cir s	.39	19.2		tbd	tbd
BI st line s	tbd	tbd		tbd	tbd
BI st line b	.39	136.2		tbd	tbd
Eleuthra deep-deep	tbd	tbd		tbd	tbd
Eleuthra surface-deep	tbd	tbd		tbd	tbd

TABLE 2. CW PARAMETERS

data type	MFSK		DPSK 10ms		DPSK 20ms	
Location	SNR/bit dB	ber %	SNR/bit dB	ber %	SNR/bit dB	ber %
Narr. Bay			tbd	6		
BI 258 s	45	5	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 258 b	40	1.4	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 1242 s	36	3.7	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 1242 b	31	4.6	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 300 cir s	15	43	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI st line s	tbd av	49	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI st line b	tbd av	47	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
Eleuthra deep-deep	tbd	0.37	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
Eleuthra surface-deep	tbd	1.67	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd

TABLE 3. BIT ERROR RATES- PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENTS

data type	MFSK		DPSK 10ms		DPSK 20ms	
	SNR/bit dB	ber %	SNR/bit dB	ber %	SNR/bit dB	ber %
Narr bay			tbd	12		
BI 258 s	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 258 b	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 1242 s	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI 1242 b	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI cir s	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI st line s	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
BI st line b	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
Eleuthra deep- deep	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd
Eleuthra surf- deep	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd

TABLE 4. BIT ERROR RATE -SIMULATED ENVIRONMENTS

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REFERENCES

1. L. Estes, G. Fain, D. Carvalho, "Simulation of a shallow water acoustic telemetry channel." Proceedings of Oceans 92, IEEE, October 1992, pp 584-589.